

MINDSET TYPES AND BEHAVIORAL ENGAGEMENT TOWARDS MATHEMATICS AMONG JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN LAUBACH INSTITUTE

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Mindset Types and Behavioral Engagement towards Mathematics among Junior High School Students in Laubach Institute

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Abstract

This study, conducted at Laubach Institute during the S.Y. 2023-2024, aimed to determine the mindset towards mathematics and behavioral engagement among junior high school students. The respondents were 141 students, and the study used a descriptive-correlational research design with survey questionnaires and open-ended interview questions. The data were analyzed using means, standard deviation, and Pearson r correlation at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that Grade 9 students had the highest mean value of 2.47 for a fixed mindset, rated as "disagree," while Grade 7 had the lowest mean value of 2.28, also rated as "disagree." The overall mean for a fixed mindset was 2.40. For the growth mindset, Grade 8 students had the highest mean value of 3.14, rated as "agree," and Grade 9 had the lowest mean value of 2.96, also rated as "agree." The overall mean for a growth mindset was 3.07. In terms of behavioral engagement, Grade 7 had the highest mean value of 3.41 for attendance, rated as "sometimes," while Grade 9 had the lowest mean value of 3.00. For attention, Grade 7 again had the highest mean value of 3.04, while Grade 9 had the lowest mean value of 2.91. For participation, Grade 10 had the highest mean value of 2.81, while Grade 7 had the lowest mean value of 2.69. For compliance, Grade 8 had the highest mean value of 2.93, while Grade 10 had the lowest mean value of 2.75. The study found a significant correlation between the growth mindset and behavioral engagement in terms of participation and compliance for Grade 7 students. Specifically, Grade 7 had an r -value of 0.351 for participation, interpreted as "Low Positive," and a p -value of 0.00, indicating significance. For compliance, Grade 7 had an r -value of 0.566, interpreted as "Moderately Positive," and a p -value of 0.00, also indicating significance. Grades 8, 9, and 10 had p -values greater than 0.05 for both participation and compliance, indicating no significant correlation. This suggests that younger students' growth mindsets are positively influenced by all domains of behavioral engagement.

Keywords: *mindset towards mathematics, junior high school, fixed mindset, growth mindset, behavioral engagement*

Introduction

Mathematics requires a specific mindset that includes attitudes, beliefs, and perceptions, influencing how students approach learning and problem-solving (Mazana et al., 2018). Mindset shapes individuals' thoughts, feelings, and behaviors, impacting their success or failure in various situations (Kendra, 2022; Mohd Abbas, 2023). Carol Dweck (2000) identified two beliefs about intelligence: a fixed mindset, where intelligence is innate and unchangeable, and a growth mindset, where intelligence can be developed through effort. While a fixed mindset can lead to negative thinking, it doesn't imply a lack of intelligence. In contrast, a growth mindset perceives intelligence as malleable and emphasizes effort and development (Smith, 2020). Kaya and Karakoc (2022) and Daly et al. (2019) noted that math mindsets are similar to general intelligence mindsets, categorizing individuals into 'fixed math mindsets' or 'growth math mindsets' based on their beliefs about innate or developable mathematical ability.

Filipino students' performance in mathematics is notably low compared to global standards, as shown by the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) and the National Achievement Test (NAT) results (Allan et al., 2022; Hernando, 2019). Mindsets can significantly impact learning across subjects, with math being particularly susceptible to fixed mindset views. Adopting a growth mindset in math can positively influence students' motivation and achievement by emphasizing improvement and perseverance (Miller, 2020).

Student engagement is crucial for understanding academic behavior and instructional effectiveness. It provides insights into students' activities and is vital for designing effective teaching strategies (Defino, 2019). Behavioral engagement, which includes attendance, attention, participation, and compliance, is a key factor for academic success. Engaged students tend to exhibit better cognitive processing and learning outcomes (Harbour et al., 2015; Gandiongco et al., 2016; Fredericks et al., 2010; Sleigh & Ritzer, 2012; Benassi, Overson & Hakala, 2013; Neville, 2014). The importance of behavioral engagement lies in its correlation with enhanced learning when students are curious and interested, as opposed to being disinterested or "disengaged" (Sparks, 2013).

While Dweck's (2000) concept demonstrated the influence of mindset on achievement and motivation, empirical research on the relationship between mathematics mindsets and behavioral engagement in Philippine education is lacking. This study aimed to fill this gap by exploring the connection between math mindsets and behavioral engagement among Philippine learners for the first time. The study aims to assess Junior High School students fixed and growth mindsets, as well as their behavioral engagement in terms of attendance, attention, participation, and compliance in mathematics. It seeks to determine if there is a significant relationship between students' mindset towards mathematics and their behavioral engagement. The researchers believe that understanding students' beliefs

about math is crucial as it can impact their academic performance and engagement. Their personal observations indicate that mindset influences their own attitudes and performance in mathematics.

The study focuses on students from the Laubach Institute in Poblacion, Bacolod, Lanao del Norte, who are exposed to math subjects from grades 7 to 10. A pre-test was administered to evaluate the students' retention of mathematical concepts, with results showing that 67% of students failed, highlighting significant challenges in math knowledge retention. This prompted the researchers to delve deeper into the relationship between students' mindsets towards math and their behavioral engagement for the academic year 2023-2024.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the Mindset towards Mathematics among Junior High School Students and behavioral engagement in Laubach Institute during the S.Y 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of mindset in terms of fixed and growth towards mathematics among Junior High School Students?
2. What is the level of behavioral engagement in terms of attendance, attention, participation, and compliance among Junior High School Students?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of fixed mindset towards mathematics among students and their level of behavioral engagement in terms of attendance, attention, participation, and compliance?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of growth mindset towards mathematics among students and their level of behavioral engagement in terms of attendance, attention, participation, and compliance?

Methodology

Research Design

The research employed a descriptive-correlational approach to study the relationship between students' mindset towards mathematics and their behavioral engagement. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection, focusing on identifying significant relationships between the variables without researcher intervention (Bhandari 2021).

Participants

The study was conducted at Laubach Institute in Poblacion, Bacolod, Lanao del Norte. Established in 1948 by Eusebio G. Bernales, Sr., the school offers both Junior and Senior High School programs and currently enrolls 264 students. The location was chosen for its accessibility and proximity to the researchers. The respondents were 141 Junior High School students from Laubach Institute for the academic year 2023-2024, selected due to their proximity and accessibility to the researchers.

Instruments

The research utilized a modified questionnaire based on previous studies (Dweck, 2006 & Angni et al., 2015) and structured open-ended interview questions. The questionnaire comprised two parts: the first assessed students' mindset (fixed and growth), and the second focused on their behavioral engagement. Responses were rated on a four-point and five-point scale, respectively. Research validation involved consultations with the research adviser, incorporating corrections, recommendations, and suggestions to finalize the survey and interview questions.

Procedure

Data collection began with obtaining permission from the school principal. Upon approval, the researchers distributed the revised questionnaires to the participants. The collected data was then organized for statistical analysis.

Data Analysis

Statistical tools used for data analysis included Mean and Standard Deviation to analyze responses on mindset and behavioral engagement, and Pearson r Correlation to determine significant relationships between independent and dependent variables.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were adhered to by obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring voluntary participation, confidentiality, and the absence of psychological harm to the respondents. These considerations were outlined in the informed consent form provided to the participants.

Results and Discussion

The Level of Mindset in terms of Fixed and Growth towards Mathematics Among Junior High School Students.

Table 1 presents the mean and standard deviation of the fixed mindset and growth mindset of the student participants.

Table 1 presents data about the student's level of fixed mindset towards mathematics. The table shows that among the four grade levels, Grade 9 got the highest mean value of 2.47, rated as "disagree". Meanwhile, the Grade 7 got the lowest mean value of 2.28 yet rated

also as “disagree”. The computed total mean was 2.40 rated as “disagree”. It can be seen that the fixed mindset of the grade level had a description of disagree. This means that majority of all the junior high school students answered somewhat true in all the indicators of fixed mindset.

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Level of Fixed Mindset

Respondents	Fixed Mindset			
	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Grade 7 (n=32)	2.28	.58	Disagree	Somewhat true to me
Grade 8(n=27)	2.34	.56	Disagree	Somewhat true to me
Grade 9(n=41)	2.47	.44	Disagree	Somewhat true to me
Grade 10(n=41)	2.39	.50	Disagree	Somewhat true to me
Overall (n=141)	2.40	.49	Disagree	Somewhat true to me

Legend: 3.50-4.00- Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.49- Agree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; below 1.49 Strongly Disagree

The result implies that junior high school students “somewhat” or slightly believed that mathematics is only for mathematically inclined students. The overall mean description qualitatively described as “Disagree” means that they somewhat believed that their intelligence in math cannot be changed and that having a fixed mindset about the subject can still help them understand the lesson. Several researchers observed that a fixed mindset predicted lower motivation, negative emotions, and lower achievement (Blackwell et al., 2007).

Thematic Analysis: Fixed Mindset Towards Mathematics

In interviews with students exploring their mindsets towards mathematics, a significant portion of respondents expressed a fixed mindset. Their perspectives shed light on their beliefs about the inherent difficulty of mathematics and the role of innate talent.

Theme 1: Perception of Innate Ability

A prevalent theme among the respondents was the belief that mathematical ability is innate and fixed. One student remarked, "I believe that math is a talent, it is something that you were born with. For me, I have a fixed mindset I just couldn't understand how mathematics works and I'm not really good at it." This perspective suggests a belief that mathematical skills are predetermined and not easily developed through effort or learning.

Theme 2: Challenges and Negative Experiences

Students with a fixed mindset often cited personal challenges and negative experiences with mathematics. They described struggles with remembering numbers and signs, as well as difficulties comprehending mathematical concepts despite diligent study. One student expressed, "Fixed because no matter what I do, even if I study well, I can't do the math. For me, Math is really hard and there is also a teacher who couldn't teach the math lessons well." This theme highlights the impact of past experiences and perceived limitations on their mindset towards mathematics.

Theme 3: Influence of Teaching Quality

Another recurrent theme was the influence of teachers on students' mindset towards mathematics. Some students attributed their fixed mindset to ineffective teaching methods or inadequate teacher support. They mentioned instances where they struggled due to perceived shortcomings in teaching quality. This sentiment was captured in one student's statement, "Fixed, because not all people are good in math, and for me, math is really hard as I can easily forget the numbers and signs." This theme underscores the importance of supportive and effective teaching practices in shaping students' perceptions and attitudes towards mathematics.

The thematic analysis underscores the challenge of addressing fixed mindsets among students towards mathematics. These beliefs can hinder motivation, engagement, and ultimately, academic achievement in the subject. Educators must recognize the impact of students' beliefs about their mathematical abilities and adopt strategies to promote a growth mindset. Techniques such as fostering a positive learning environment, providing personalized support, and emphasizing effort and resilience can help students overcome fixed mindsets and develop a more positive outlook towards mathematics.

Understanding students' mindsets towards mathematics is crucial for educators to design effective teaching strategies and support mechanisms. By addressing fixed mindsets through targeted interventions and promoting a growth-oriented approach, educators can empower students to cultivate confidence, persistence, and enthusiasm in learning mathematics. This approach not only enhances academic performance but also fosters lifelong learning skills essential for success in diverse academic and professional endeavors.

“Fixed, because not all people are good in math, and for me, math is really hard as I can easily forget the numbers and signs.”

“Fixed because no matter what I do, even if I study well, I can't do the math. For me, Math is really hard and there is also a teacher who couldn't teach the math lessons well.”

“I believe that math is a talent, it is something that you were born with. For me, I have a fixed mindset I just couldn't understand how mathematics works and I'm not really good at it.”

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Level of Growth Mindset

Respondents	Growth Mindset			
	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Grade 7 (n=32)	3.08	.80	Agree	True to me
Grade 8(n=27)	3.14	.98	Agree	True to me
Grade 9(n=41)	2.96	.48	Agree	True to me
Grade 10(n=41)	3.10	.42	Agree	True to me
Overall (n=141)	3.07	.81	Agree	True to me

Legend: 3.50-4.00- Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.49- Agree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; below 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 2 presents data about the student's level of growth mindset towards mathematics. The table shows that among the four grade levels, Grade 8 got the highest mean value of 3.14 rated as "Agree". Meanwhile, Grade 9 got the lowest mean value of 2.96 yet rated also as "Agree". The computed total mean was 3.07 rated as "Agree". It can be seen that the growth mindset of all the grade levels had a description of agree. This means that the majority of the junior high school students answered true to me in all the indicators of growth mindset.

The result revealed that the junior high school students "agreed" or believed that their intelligence in mathematics could still improve. Moreover, the overall mean and the mean by grade level shows a qualitative description of "Agree" which indicates that indicators under the growth mindset were agreed "True to me". The standard deviation which implies that the responses of the students were closer to the mean. This means that junior high school participants agreed that if they have a positive growth mindset, they believed that they can do mathematics better.

Thematic Analysis: Mindset Towards Mathematics

In an interview exploring students' mindsets towards mathematics, respondents expressed their perspectives, revealing insights into how mindset influences their learning experiences.

Theme 1: Growth Mindset and Belief in Learning

The majority of students interviewed identified with a growth mindset towards mathematics. They emphasized the belief that mathematical skills can be developed through effort and persistence. For instance, one student stated, "Growth mindset because I believe that math is easy to understand and it is very easy for me to solve it as well, the more I grow older the more I improve and develop my skills in my math class." This sentiment underscores their positive outlook on learning and improvement over time.

Theme 2: Teacher Influence and Learning Environment

Students highlighted the crucial role of teachers in shaping their mindset towards mathematics. They expressed appreciation for teachers who effectively communicate mathematical concepts and make learning accessible. One participant noted, "Growth, because I believe that if all students will study, there will be an improvement I think it's really helpful that my teacher is really good in teaching math and she makes it easier for us to understand her discussion." This theme emphasizes that supportive and skilled teaching fosters a positive mindset and enhances students' confidence in tackling mathematical challenges.

Theme 3: Impact of Mindset on Learning Outcomes

The discussion revealed that students' mindset significantly influences their engagement and performance in mathematics. Those with a growth mindset expressed more enthusiasm for learning and were more likely to engage actively in class activities. Conversely, students with a fixed mindset, as discussed in previous studies (Miller, 2020), may face challenges in embracing mathematical concepts and engaging fully in classroom activities.

The themes identified underscore the importance of nurturing a growth mindset among students to enhance their learning experiences in mathematics. Teachers play a pivotal role in creating a supportive learning environment where students feel encouraged to explore mathematical concepts and persist through challenges. Strategies such as providing constructive feedback, promoting a growth-oriented classroom culture, and offering differentiated instruction can help cultivate a positive mindset and improve overall learning outcomes.

The thematic analysis highlights that students' mindset towards mathematics significantly influences their learning experiences and outcomes. By fostering a growth mindset and leveraging effective teaching strategies, educators can empower students to approach mathematics with confidence, curiosity, and resilience. This approach not only enhances mathematical proficiency but also nurtures lifelong learning skills essential for academic success and personal development.

The Level of Behavioral Engagement in terms of their Attendance, Attention, Participation, and Compliance Among Junior High School Students.

Table 3 presents the behavioral engagement of the students in terms of their attendance, attention, participation, and compliance.

Table 3 provides insights into students' behavioral engagement specifically in terms of attendance across different grade levels within the context of mathematics education.

Table 3. Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Level of Behavioral Engagement in terms of Attendance

Respondents	Attendance			
	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Grade 7 (n=32)	3.41	.67	Sometimes	Moderately Observed
Grade 8 (n=27)	3.13	.70	Sometimes	Moderately Observed
Grade 9 (n=41)	3.00	.55	Sometimes	Moderately Observed
Grade 10 (n=41)	3.25	.60	Sometimes	Moderately Observed
Overall (n=141)	3.16	.58	Sometimes	Moderately Observed

Legend: 5.00-4.50- Always (A); 4.50-3.49- Often (O); 2.50-3.49 Sometimes (S); Seldom 1.5-2.49; Never (N) -Below 1.49

The findings reveal that Grade 7 students achieved the highest mean value of 3.41, indicating that their attendance is rated as "Sometimes," which is interpreted as moderately observed. Conversely, Grade 9 students obtained the lowest mean value of 3.00, also rated as "Sometimes," suggesting a similar level of moderately observed attendance.

The ratings of "Sometimes" for both Grade 7 and Grade 9 suggest that students in these grade levels attend mathematics classes with a moderate frequency. This level of attendance could be influenced by various factors such as student motivation, perceived importance of mathematics, personal interest, and external circumstances affecting attendance patterns.

Grade 7 students, with a mean value of 3.41, exhibit moderately observed attendance. This suggests that, on average, they attend mathematics classes regularly but may occasionally miss sessions. Educators can build on this by reinforcing the importance of consistent attendance and its correlation with academic success. Strategies such as setting clear attendance expectations, communicating the relevance of class activities, and providing incentives for regular attendance could further enhance student participation.

Grade 9 students, with a mean value of 3.00, also demonstrate moderately observed attendance. This indicates a slightly lower attendance frequency compared to Grade 7. Educators may need to explore factors contributing to sporadic attendance among Grade 9 students, such as scheduling conflicts, academic pressures, or disengagement from mathematics content. Addressing these factors through proactive communication, individualized support, and targeted interventions can help improve attendance rates and subsequently enhance learning outcomes.

Comparing attendance levels across Grade 7 and Grade 9 highlights differences in student attendance patterns within the same educational environment. Understanding these variations can inform educators' efforts to promote consistent attendance and foster a conducive learning atmosphere conducive to student success.

To encourage regular attendance across all grade levels, educators can implement strategies that emphasize the relevance of mathematics education in everyday life, create engaging learning experiences, and establish a supportive classroom climate. Collaborative efforts involving teachers, administrators, and families can also play a crucial role in promoting a positive school attendance culture.

Table 3 underscores the significance of monitoring and addressing student attendance as part of enhancing behavioral engagement in mathematics education. By fostering a supportive and engaging learning environment and implementing targeted strategies to promote regular attendance, educators can optimize student participation, learning outcomes, and overall academic success in mathematics and beyond. This proactive approach not only supports immediate educational goals but also contributes to long-term student achievement and well-being.

Table 4. Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Level of Behavioral Engagement in terms of Attention

Respondents	Attention			
	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Grade 7 (n=32)	3.04	.72	Sometimes	Moderately Observed
Grade 8 (n=27)	3.00	.73	Sometimes	Moderately Observed
Grade 9 (n=41)	2.91	.55	Sometimes	Moderately Observed
Grade10 (n=41)	3.02	.60	Sometimes	Moderately Observed
Overall (n=141)	3.00	.58	Sometimes	Moderately Observed

Legend: 5.00-4.50- Always (A); 4.50-3.49- Often (O); 2.50-3.49 Sometimes (S); Seldom 1.5-2.49; Never (N) -Below 1.49

Table 4 provides an analysis of students' behavioral engagement in terms of attention across different grade levels, shedding light on their focus and concentration during mathematics classes.

The results indicate that Grade 7 students achieved the highest mean value of 3.04, which corresponds to a rating of "Sometimes," interpreted as moderately observed attention. Conversely, Grade 9 students obtained the lowest mean value of 2.91, also rated as "Sometimes," indicating a similar level of moderately observed attention.

The ratings of "Sometimes" for both Grade 7 and Grade 9 suggest that students in these grade levels exhibit moderate attention during

mathematics lessons. This level of attention could be influenced by factors such as lesson content, teaching methods, classroom environment, and individual student preferences.

Grade 7 students, with a mean value of 3.04, demonstrate moderately observed attention in class. This could imply that they generally engage with lesson content and exhibit focused behavior during instructional periods. Educators may capitalize on this by fostering interactive learning experiences that maintain their interest and active participation.

Grade 9 students, with a mean value of 2.91, also display moderately observed attention. This grade level's slightly lower rating suggests a need to explore strategies that enhance sustained focus and concentration during mathematical instruction. Teachers could consider incorporating varied teaching techniques, visual aids, or interactive activities to sustain student engagement and minimize distractions.

Comparing the attention levels across Grade 7 and Grade 9 highlights subtle differences in how students of different ages interact with classroom content. Understanding these variations can guide educators in tailoring their instructional approaches to effectively meet the needs and preferences of students at different developmental stages.

To enhance attention levels across both grades, educators can adopt strategies that promote active learning and maintain student interest throughout lessons. These may include incorporating real-world applications of mathematical concepts, providing opportunities for collaborative learning, and offering timely feedback to reinforce student understanding.

Table 4 underscores the importance of addressing student attention as a critical component of effective mathematics instruction. By fostering a supportive learning environment and employing engaging teaching strategies, educators can optimize students' focus and concentration, thereby enhancing their overall learning experiences and academic achievement in mathematics. This proactive approach not only supports immediate classroom success but also cultivates lifelong skills essential for continued academic growth.

Table 5. *Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Level of Behavioral Engagement in terms of Participation*

Respondents	Participation			
	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Grade 7 (n=32)	2.69	.79	Sometimes	Moderately Observed
Grade 8 (n=27)	2.77	.78	Sometimes	Moderately Observed
Grade 9 (n=41)	2.73	.65	Sometimes	Moderately Observed
Grade10 (n=41)	2.81	.65	Sometimes	Moderately Observed
Overall (n=141)	2.74	.67	Sometimes	Moderately Observed

Legend: 5.00-4.50- Always (A); 4.50-3.49- Often (O); 2.50-3.49 Sometimes (S); Seldom 1.5–2.49; Never (N) -Below 1.49

Table 5 reveals the behavioral engagement of students in terms of their participation across different grade levels, providing insights into their active involvement in classroom activities.

The findings indicate that Grade 10 students attained the highest mean value of 2.81, which corresponds to a rating of "Sometimes," indicating moderate participation. Conversely, Grade 7 students obtained the lowest mean value of 2.69, also rated as "Sometimes," suggesting a similar level of moderate participation.

The ratings of "Sometimes" for both Grade 10 and Grade 7 imply that while students participate in classroom activities, their engagement is not consistently high. This moderate level of participation could stem from various factors, such as individual confidence levels, interest in the subject matter, or instructional strategies employed by teachers.

For Grade 10 students, achieving a mean value of 2.81 suggests that they participate moderately in class activities. This could indicate that they are somewhat engaged but may not consistently contribute to discussions or group work. It's essential for educators to explore ways to further motivate these students to increase their involvement actively. Strategies such as incorporating more interactive lessons, encouraging peer collaboration, or providing opportunities for leadership roles could enhance their participation.

Grade 7 students, with a mean value of 2.69, also participate moderately. This grade level's slightly lower participation might reflect early adolescent dynamics, where students are still adjusting to new academic expectations and social environments. Teachers can consider implementing strategies that cater to their developmental stage, such as differentiated instruction and fostering a supportive classroom culture that values all contributions.

Comparing these findings across grade levels highlights the variability in participation rates and underscores the need for tailored instructional approaches. While both grades exhibit moderate participation levels, understanding the underlying reasons behind these behaviors is crucial. Factors such as self-perception, peer influence, and instructional methods play pivotal roles in shaping student engagement.

In conclusion, the findings from Table 5 underscore the importance of enhancing student participation in classroom activities to foster a more dynamic learning environment. By addressing factors that influence engagement and implementing targeted interventions, educators can cultivate a culture of active participation and promote deeper learning experiences for students across different grade levels. This approach not only supports academic growth but also nurtures students' confidence and sense of belonging in their

mathematical learning journey.

Table 6. Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Level of Behavioral Engagement in terms of Compliance

Respondents	Compliance			
	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Grade 7 (n=32)	2.91	.70	Sometimes	Moderately Observed
Grade 8 (n=27)	2.93	.65	Sometimes	Moderately Observed
Grade 9 (n=41)	2.81	.60	Sometimes	Moderately Observed
Grade10 (n=41)	2.75	.67	Sometimes	Moderately Observed
Overall (n=141)	2.83	.62	Sometimes	Moderately Observed

Legend: 5.00-4.50- Always (A); 4.50-3.49- Often (O); 2.50-3.49 Sometimes (S); Seldom 1.5--2.49; Never (N) -Below 1.49

Table 6 presents the behavioral engagement of the students in terms of their compliance. The result shows that in terms of compliance, Grade 8 got the highest mean value of 2.93 rated as "Sometimes" which is interpreted as moderately observed, while Grade 10 got the lowest mean value of 2.75 which is rated as "Sometimes" and interpreted as moderately observed as well.

This indicates that the majority of all grade levels in junior high school students rated "Sometimes" in all the indicators of behavioral engagement in terms of attendance, attention, participation, and compliance. The result indicates that most of the junior high school students moderately observe positive behavioral engagement in the class.

Furthermore, among the behavioral engagement, participation and compliance were the lowest with a total mean of 2.74 and 2.83. In the interview with the teachers, the students had lesser participation during classroom observations and they were not highly engaged in complying with all the requirements in the subject.

Thematic Analysis: Mindset and Behavioral Engagement in Mathematics

In interviews with respondents regarding how mindset influences their behavioral engagement in mathematics, several themes emerged, shedding light on their perceptions and experiences.

Theme 1: Fear of Failure and Lack of Confidence

Respondents expressed apprehension about participating in class activities due to fear of making mistakes or not knowing the correct answers. One student remarked, "Yes, it can affect my behavioral engagement because if the teacher calls me to stand to answer, I wouldn't participate since I don't know what I would answer." This fear of being wrong or embarrassed in front of peers hindered their willingness to engage actively in classroom discussions and activities.

The fear of failure highlighted by students reflects a fixed mindset orientation, where they perceive their abilities as static and are reluctant to take risks or participate actively. This mindset can undermine their motivation and inhibit their academic progress (Dweck, 2000). Educators need to cultivate a supportive classroom environment that encourages risk-taking, values effort, and fosters a growth mindset among students (Jones, 2022).

Theme 2: Impact of Teacher Approachability and Classroom Environment

Participants also emphasized the importance of teacher approachability and a positive classroom atmosphere in influencing their engagement. One student explained, "If I understand our lesson, I will definitely participate in our class. However, I feel like I can understand our lesson more if our teacher is not strict and my classmates will not judge me if I don't get the activity right." This sentiment underscores the role of teacher-student relationships and the classroom climate in fostering student participation and learning.

The students' preference for a less strict environment suggests that an authoritative teaching style may deter engagement and hinder learning (Ganuza & Xu, 2020). Creating a safe space where students feel supported, respected, and free to make mistakes can enhance their confidence and willingness to participate actively in mathematical activities.

Theme 3: Importance of Positive Behavioral Engagement

Many students admitted that their lack of understanding or fear of judgment from peers affected their overall engagement in mathematics. They expressed that feeling accepted and free to make errors without fear of judgment would improve their learning experience. As one participant stated, "Most of the students answered that if they felt that they were not rejected and felt free to commit errors in doing the activities, they would learn the math subject better."

This theme highlights the crucial link between positive behavioral engagement and academic achievement (Gunuc, 2019). When students feel encouraged and supported, they are more likely to actively participate, take academic risks, and ultimately deepen their understanding of mathematical concepts. Teachers play a pivotal role in creating an inclusive environment that nurtures students' confidence and resilience in learning mathematics.

The thematic analysis of student responses underscores the significant influence of mindset and classroom environment on behavioral engagement in mathematics. By addressing students' fears of failure, promoting a growth mindset, and fostering a supportive learning

environment, educators can enhance student participation and improve overall academic outcomes in mathematics. Encouraging active engagement through positive reinforcement and creating opportunities for collaborative learning can further empower students to develop their mathematical skills with confidence and enthusiasm.

Significance of the Relationship Between the Students' Level of Fixed Mindset towards Mathematics and their Level of Behavioral Engagement in terms of Attendance, Attention, Participation, and Compliance.

The correlation analysis was performed to examine the relationship between the students' level of fixed mindset towards mathematics and their level of behavioral engagement in terms of attendance, attention, participation, and compliance.

Table 7 presents the correlation coefficient, degree of correlation, p-value, and the remark of the analysis for each independent variable versus the dependent variable.

Table 7. *Correlation Analysis on the Students' Level of Fixed Mindset and their Level of Behavioral Engagement in terms of Attendance*

Respondents	Attendance			
	r	Interpretation	p	Interpretation
Grade 7 (n=32)	.037	Low Positive	0.21	Not significant
Grade 8 (n=27)	.047	Moderately Positive	.05	Not significant
Grade 9 (n=41)	.047	Moderately Positive	.76	Not significant
Grade10 (n=41)	.023	Low Positive	.88	Not significant
Overall (n=141)	.007	No Correlation	.93	Not significant

Significant at 0.05 level

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the level of fixed mindset and behavioral engagement in terms of Attendance

Table 7 presents the correlation analysis of students' level of fixed mindset and their level of behavioral engagement in terms of attendance. The result shows that all the grade levels' correlation of students' level of fixed mindset and their level of behavioral engagement in terms of attendance had an overall r-value of .007 which is interpreted as "No Correlation" and an overall p-value of 0.93 which is interpreted as "Not Significant".

Table 8. *Correlation Analysis on the Students' Level of Fixed Mindset and their Level of Behavioral Engagement in terms of Attention*

Respondents	Attention			
	r	Interpretation	p	Interpretation
Grade 7 (n=32)	.420	Moderately Positive	.00	Significant
Grade 8 (n=27)	.326	Low Positive	.01	Significant
Grade 9 (n=41)	.363	Low Positive	.00	Significant
Grade10 (n=41)	.482	Moderately Positive	.00	Significant
Overall (n=141)	.347	Low Positive	.02	Significant

Significant at 0.05 level

Ho: There is a significant between the level of fixed mindset and behavioral engagement in terms of Attention

Table 8 presents the correlation analysis of students' level of fixed mindset and their level of behavioral engagement in terms of attention. The result shows that all the grade levels' correlation of students' level of fixed mindset and their level of behavioral engagement in terms of attention had an overall r- value of .347 which is interpreted as "Low Positive" and an overall p-value of 0.02 which is interpreted as "Significant".

Table 9. *Correlation Analysis on the Students' Level of Fixed Mindset and their Level of Behavioral Engagement in terms of Participation*

Respondents	Participation			
	r	Interpretation	p	Interpretation
Grade 7 (n=32)	.418	Moderately Positive	.00	Significant
Grade 8 (n=27)	.426	Moderately Positive	.00	Significant
Grade 9 (n=41)	.286	Low Positive	.04	Significant
Grade10 (n=41)	.352	Low Positive	.02	Significant
Overall (n=141)	.242	Low Positive	.00	Significant

Significant at 0.05 level

Ho: There is a significant relationship between the level of fixed mindset and behavioral engagement in terms of Participation

Table 9 provides a correlation analysis exploring how students' fixed mindset relates to their behavioral engagement in terms of participation across various grade levels. The analysis reveals an overall r-value of 0.242, interpreted as "Low Positive," with an overall p-value of 0.00, indicating statistical significance.

The findings indicate a significant relationship between students' fixed mindset and their level of participation in mathematics classes. A "Low Positive" correlation suggests that as students' fixed mindset tendencies increase—believing their abilities are fixed and unchangeable—their willingness or eagerness to actively participate in classroom activities also increases, albeit modestly.

The significant correlation observed underscores the impact of mindset on students' willingness to engage actively in learning activities. Students with a fixed mindset may approach participation with varying degrees of reluctance or hesitancy, influenced by their belief that success or failure is predetermined rather than influenced by effort and learning strategies (Yeager & Dweck, 2020).

With an overall p-value of 0.00, which is well below the conventional significance level of 0.05, the analysis provides strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This suggests that there is indeed a meaningful connection between students' fixed mindset and their level of participation in mathematics education across all grade levels studied.

To address the implications of these findings, educators can implement strategies that promote a growth mindset among students. Encouraging students to view challenges as opportunities for growth, emphasizing effort over innate ability, and providing constructive feedback can help foster a more positive and engaged learning environment (Dweck, 2000).

Table 9's correlation analysis highlights the relevance of mindset in shaping students' behavioral engagement, specifically in terms of participation in mathematics education. Understanding the influence of fixed mindsets on participation behaviors can guide educators in developing interventions that promote active involvement and deeper learning experiences among students. By nurturing a growth mindset, educators can empower students to embrace challenges, take risks, and actively contribute to their own learning journey in mathematics.

Table 10. *Correlation Analysis on the Students' Level of Fixed Mindset and their Level of Behavioral Engagement in terms of Compliance*

Respondents	Compliance			
	r	Interpretation	p	Interpretation
Grade 7 (n=32)	.253	Low Positive	.00	Significant
Grade 8 (n=27)	.281	Low Positive	.03	Significant
Grade 9 (n=41)	.277	Low Positive	.02	Significant
Grade10 (n=41)	.405	Low Positive	.00	Significant
Overall (n=141)	.227	Low Positive	.03	Significant

Significant at 0.05 level

Ho: There is a significant relationship between the level of fixed mindset and behavioral engagement in terms of Compliance

Table 10 presents the correlation analysis examining the relationship between students' fixed mindset and their behavioral engagement in terms of compliance across different grade levels. The findings reveal an overall r-value of 0.227, interpreted as "Low Positive," with an overall p-value of 0.03, indicating statistical significance.

The correlation analysis indicates that there is a statistically significant, albeit low positive relationship between students' fixed mindset and their compliance in mathematics classes across all grade levels. This suggests that students who exhibit a fixed mindset, viewing their abilities as static and unchangeable, tend to demonstrate varying degrees of compliance with classroom requirements and expectations.

Thematic Analysis

Theme 1: Fear and Avoidance Due to Fixed Mindset

Participants expressed significant fear and anxiety regarding mathematics assessments, particularly quizzes.

One respondent shared, "If we have a quiz, I feel so scared that it made me not attend my class. I am afraid that my teacher will scold me if I have a low score on our quiz." This fear of failure leads to avoidance behaviors, such as skipping classes and not participating in learning activities. Another participant echoed similar sentiments, stating, "I rather not listen to my teacher as well since I know that no matter what I do, I would not be able to understand our lesson."

The fear described by the participants is indicative of a fixed mindset, where individuals believe their abilities are fixed and cannot be improved through effort (Yeager & Dweck, 2020). This mindset can lead to a sense of helplessness and disengagement from learning activities, ultimately impacting academic performance negatively. Teachers play a crucial role in mitigating these fears by fostering a supportive learning environment that emphasizes growth and effort over innate ability.

Theme 2: Boredom and Passive Engagement

Participants also expressed feelings of boredom and disinterest in their math classes, which led to passive learning behaviors.

One student remarked, "I find my math class to be a boring one, I tend to get sleepy and didn't pay attention to my teacher discussion."

This lack of engagement results in copying classmates' work to complete assignments rather than actively participating in learning tasks.

Boredom and disinterest in mathematics classes can hinder students' motivation and engagement (Yeager & Dweck, 2020). Passive learning behaviors, such as copying assignments, indicate a lack of intrinsic motivation and genuine understanding of the subject matter. Effective teaching strategies that promote active learning and student involvement are essential to rekindling interest and fostering

meaningful engagement in mathematics.

Theme 3: Importance of Teacher Support and Classroom Environment

Participants highlighted the critical role of teachers in creating a positive and engaging classroom environment. One respondent emphasized the need for teachers to support struggling students, stating, "Teachers should help the students on creating a positive learning environment so that they will have excellent academic performance." Participants also stressed the importance of teacher expertise in adapting teaching styles and assessing student learning effectively.

Teachers' ability to create a positive learning environment is paramount in supporting students' academic success and fostering a growth mindset (Dweck, 2000). This environment should encourage risk-taking, effort, and resilience in the face of challenges. Teacher training in pedagogical strategies that accommodate diverse learning needs and address misconceptions is crucial for enhancing classroom engagement and promoting meaningful learning experiences (Delfin, 2020).

The thematic analysis of participant responses underscores the complex interplay between mindset, engagement, and academic performance in mathematics education. Fear, boredom, and the need for supportive teaching practices emerged as central themes influencing students' behavioral engagement. Addressing these factors through effective instructional strategies and cultivating a growth mindset can significantly enhance student motivation and achievement in mathematics. Teachers play a pivotal role in creating conducive learning environments that empower students to overcome challenges and thrive academically.

Significance of the Relationship Between the Students' Level of Growth Mindset towards Mathematics and their Level of Behavioral Engagement in terms of Attendance, Attention, Participation, and Compliance.

The correlation analysis was performed to examine the relationship between the students' level of growth mindset toward mathematics and their level of behavioral engagement in terms of attendance, attention, participation, and compliance.

Table 10 presents the correlation coefficient, degree of correlation, p-value, and the remark of the analysis for each independent variable versus the dependent variable.

Table 11. *Correlation and Analysis on the Students' Level of Growth Mindset and their Level of Behavioral Engagement in terms of Attendance*

Respondents	Attendance			
	<i>r</i>	Interpretation	<i>p</i>	Interpretation
Grade 7 (n=32)	.330	Low Positive	.01	Significant
Grade 8 (n=27)	.072	Negligible Correlation	.32	Not significant
Grade 9 (n=41)	-.139	Negligible Correlation	.38	Not significant
Grade10 (n=41)	.104	Negligible Correlation	.51	Not significant
Overall (n=141)	.071	Negligible Correlation	.40	Not significant

Significant at 0.05 level

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the level of growth mindset and behavioral engagement in terms of Attendance

Table 11 provides a detailed examination of the correlation between students' growth mindset and their behavioral engagement in terms of attendance across different grade levels. This analysis sheds light on how mindset influences attendance behaviors within the context of mathematics education.

Among the grade levels studied, Grade 7 exhibits a significant correlation between growth mindset and attendance, with an r-value of 0.330, indicating a "Low Positive" relationship. This finding suggests that Grade 7 students who embrace a growth mindset—believing in the potential to develop their abilities through effort—are more likely to demonstrate consistent attendance in their mathematics classes. The associated p-value of 0.01 underscores the statistical significance of this correlation, reinforcing the reliability of the observed relationship.

In contrast, Grades 8, 9, and 10 show correlations that are not statistically significant, as indicated by p-values exceeding 0.05. This implies that for these higher grade levels, there is insufficient evidence to support a meaningful association between students' growth mindset and their attendance patterns in mathematics education. This variability in findings underscores the importance of considering developmental stages and educational contexts when interpreting such correlations.

These results align with previous research indicating that younger students may be more responsive to interventions promoting a growth mindset, which can positively impact attendance and overall engagement in academic settings (Dweck, 2000; Claro & Paunesku, 2014). Effective strategies may include fostering a supportive school environment, encouraging intrinsic motivation through meaningful learning experiences, and emphasizing the importance of regular attendance for academic success.

The findings from Table 11 highlight the nuanced relationship between growth mindset and attendance among junior high school students. While Grade 7 shows a significant positive correlation, Grades 8, 9, and 10 demonstrate no significant associations. These findings suggest that targeted interventions aimed at promoting growth mindset and enhancing attendance behaviors should consider the unique needs and challenges of students at different stages of secondary education. Future research could explore additional factors influencing attendance patterns and further validate these findings across diverse educational contexts to inform comprehensive

strategies for improving student engagement and academic outcomes.

Table 12. *Correlation and Analysis on the Students' Level of Growth Mindset and their Level of Behavioral Engagement in terms of Attention*

Respondents	Attention			
	<i>r</i>	Interpretation	<i>p</i>	Interpretation
Grade 7 (n=32)	.579	Moderately Positive	.00	Significant
Grade 8 (n=27)	.140	Negligible Correlation	.07	Not significant
Grade 9 (n=41)	-.059	Negligible Correlation	.71	Not significant
Grade10 (n=41)	.093	Negligible Correlation	.56	Not significant
Overall (n=141)	.167	Negligible Correlation	.05	Not significant

Significant at 0.05 level

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the level of growth mindset and behavioral engagement in terms of Attention

Table 12 provides a comprehensive analysis of the correlation between students' growth mindset and their behavioral engagement specifically in terms of attention across various grade levels. This analysis reveals notable insights into how mindset influences attention in the context of mathematics education.

Among the grade levels examined, Grade 7 emerges as significant with a notably strong correlation between growth mindset and attention, characterized by an *r*-value of 0.579, indicating a "Moderately Positive" relationship. This finding suggests that Grade 7 students who possess a growth mindset—believing in the potential for improvement through effort—are more likely to exhibit focused attention during mathematical tasks and discussions. The associated *p*-value of 0.00 underscores the statistical significance of this correlation, reinforcing the reliability of the observed relationship.

Conversely, Grades 8, 9, and 10 demonstrate correlations that are not statistically significant, as evidenced by *p*-values exceeding 0.05. This implies that for these higher grade levels, there is insufficient evidence to support a meaningful association between students' growth mindset and their level of attention in mathematics classes. This variability in findings across different grade levels underscores the importance of considering developmental stages and educational contexts when interpreting such correlations.

These results are consistent with existing literature suggesting that younger students may be more receptive to interventions promoting a growth mindset, which in turn enhances their ability to maintain sustained attention and engagement in academic tasks (Dweck, 2000; Claro & Paunesku, 2014). Effective strategies may include cultivating a supportive classroom environment, providing opportunities for self-directed learning, and reinforcing the value of persistence and resilience in learning.

The findings from Table 12 underscore the nuanced relationship between growth mindset and attention among junior high school students. While Grade 7 students show a significant positive correlation, Grades 8, 9, and 10 exhibit no significant associations. These findings suggest that educational interventions targeting mindset and attention should be tailored to the specific developmental needs and academic challenges of students at different stages of secondary education. Future research could further explore additional factors influencing attention and validate these findings across diverse educational settings to inform effective pedagogical practices and student support strategies.

Table 13. *Correlation and Analysis on the Students' Level of Growth Mindset and their Level of Behavioral Engagement in terms of Participation*

Respondents	Participation			
	<i>r</i>	Interpretation	<i>p</i>	Interpretation
Grade 7 (n=32)	.351	Low Positive	.00	Significant
Grade 8 (n=27)	-.152	Negligible Correlation	.16	Not significant
Grade 9 (n=41)	-.043	Negligible Correlation	.78	Not significant
Grade10 (n=41)	-.172	Negligible Correlation	.28	Not significant
Overall (n=141)	-.021	Negligible Correlation	.08	Not significant

Significant at 0.05 level

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the level of growth mindset and behavioral engagement in terms of Participation

The correlation analysis presented in Table 13 examines the relationship between students' growth mindset and their behavioral engagement specifically in terms of participation across different grade levels. The findings highlight distinct patterns among the grades studied.

Grade 7 stands out with a significant correlation between growth mindset and participation, characterized by an *r*-value of 0.351, indicating a "Low Positive" relationship. This suggests that as students in Grade 7 exhibit more of a growth mindset—believing in the malleability of their abilities and valuing effort—they also tend to engage more actively in class participation related to mathematics. The associated *p*-value of 0.00 underscores the statistical significance of this correlation, reinforcing the reliability of the observed relationship.

In contrast, Grades 8, 9, and 10 show correlations that are not statistically significant, as indicated by *p*-values greater than 0.05. This implies that for these grade levels, there is no substantial evidence to suggest a meaningful relationship between students' growth

mindset and their level of participation in mathematical activities. This finding is crucial as it suggests variability in how growth mindset influences behavioral engagement across different stages of junior high school education.

The results align with previous research indicating that younger students, such as those in Grade 7, may be more responsive to interventions promoting a growth mindset, which in turn enhances their active participation in learning activities (Dweck, 2000; Claro & Paunesku, 2014). These interventions may include emphasizing the importance of effort, providing constructive feedback, and fostering a supportive classroom environment where students feel encouraged to take academic risks.

Overall, the findings underscore the importance of considering developmental differences when designing educational strategies aimed at fostering positive academic behaviors. While Grade 7 students demonstrate a significant correlation between growth mindset and participation, Grades 8, 9, and 10 exhibit non-significant associations, suggesting the need for tailored approaches to sustain engagement and motivation across different stages of secondary education. Future research could explore additional factors that might influence these relationships and further refine strategies to promote students' adaptive mindsets and enhance their educational outcomes.

Table 14. *Correlation and Analysis on the Students' Level of Growth Mindset and their Level of Behavioral Engagement in terms of Compliance*

Respondents	Compliance			
	<i>r</i>	Interpretation	<i>p</i>	Interpretation
Grade 7 (n=32)	.566	Moderately Positive	.00	Significant
Grade 8 (n=27)	-.341	Negligible Correlation	.25	Not significant
Grade 9 (n=41)	-.203	Negligible Correlation	.16	Not significant
Grade10 (n=41)	.063	Negligible Correlation	.69	Not significant
Overall (n=141)	.081	Negligible Correlation	.34	Not significant

Significant at 0.05 level

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the level of growth mindset and behavioral engagement in terms of Compliance

Table 14 presents the correlation analysis of students' level of growth mindset and their level of behavioral engagement in terms of compliance. The result shows that among all the grade levels' correlation of students' level of growth mindset and their level of behavioral engagement in terms of compliance, only Grade 7 had an *r*-value of .566 which is interpreted as "Moderately Positive" and a *p*-value of 0.00 which is interpreted as "Significant". Grades 8, 9, and 10 all had *p*-values greater than 0.05 which are interpreted as "Not Significant".

As presented on the tables, only grade 7 had a *p*-value less than 0.05 level of significance. This signifies that there is a significant relationship between grade 7 students' Level of Growth Mindset and their level of Behavioral Engagement in terms of attendance, attention, participation, and compliance. This means that among the four grade levels, only the grade 7 student's level of growth mindset has positively correlated to their level of behavioral engagement in terms of attendance, attention, participation, and compliance. This implies that at a young age, students' growth mindset is affected by all the domains of behavioral engagement.

Thematic Analysis and Discussion

Theme 1. Usefulness and Practicality of Mathematics

A recurring theme in the interviews was the recognition of the practical applications of mathematics in daily life. One respondent noted, "Mathematics is very useful in our lives, just by simply learning how to count and to budget our daily expenses is really helpful for us." This highlights the students' understanding of the relevance of math skills beyond the classroom. The same respondent further illustrated the impact of teacher support: "When my teacher gave us an activity to solve, I always thought that it would be hard from the very moment I saw the problem but when my teacher showed us how to solve it and encouraged us to solve it, I realized that it wasn't that hard." This underscores the role of practical demonstrations and teacher encouragement in shifting students' perceptions of difficulty in math tasks.

Theme 2. Intrinsic Motivation and Positive Attitude

Intrinsic motivation and a positive attitude towards mathematics were also evident. One student expressed their enthusiasm and commitment: "I'm always present and excited to attend our math class, I don't like to skip my math subject and I love math. I am also competitive and willing to join math competitions and do my math assignments on time." This student's proactive engagement and excitement for math highlight the powerful effect of intrinsic motivation. Research by Claro and Paunesku (2014) supports this, noting that students with a growth mindset are more likely to excel due to their recognition of effort and the pursuit of academic success.

Theme 3. Teacher's Influence on Student Engagement

The influence of teacher demeanor on student engagement emerged as a significant theme. A student mentioned, "Even I'm not mathematically inclined I still listen to my teacher discussion so I can understand our lesson and for me to be able to answer our quizzes. I also try participating in various activities to hone my mathematical skills. But still, I am more comfortable to learn if my teacher is approachable and not too strict." This highlights the importance of teacher approachability and a supportive classroom environment in fostering student engagement, even among those who do not initially feel confident in their mathematical abilities. Shernoff and

Hoogstra (2019) suggest that engaging activities, when combined with a positive emotional environment, significantly enhance learner engagement.

Theme 4. Impact of Growth Mindset

Students' responses indicate that a growth mindset positively affects their engagement in mathematics. The realization that effort and practice can lead to improvement was apparent. For instance, one student reflected on their change in perception after receiving encouragement from their teacher, realizing the problems were not as difficult as initially thought. This aligns with the findings of Claro and Paunesku (2014), who found that students with a growth mindset are more likely to embrace challenges and value critical feedback, leading to better academic performance.

Theme 5. Classroom Dynamics and Peer Interactions

The theme of classroom dynamics and peer interactions also emerged. Students believed that understanding the lesson was facilitated by a non-judgmental and supportive environment. They mentioned that both teacher approachability and peer support were crucial. Engagement in mathematics, as suggested by Azebedo, Disessa, and Sherin (2019), is more intense and of higher quality when students feel excited and committed to the activities. This view is supported by students' sentiments that they perform better in a positive and non-judgmental classroom atmosphere.

Theme 6. Practical Applications and Engagement

The practical applications of mathematics in everyday life and direct involvement in math-related activities significantly influenced student engagement. Students who saw the relevance of math in real-life scenarios were more motivated to participate and understand the subject. As one student mentioned, practical activities demonstrated by the teacher made the problems seem less daunting. Shernoff and Hoogstra (2019) emphasize that activities perceived as relevant and challenging are more likely to engage students, providing intrinsic satisfaction and building a foundation of interest for the future.

The thematic analysis of student interviews revealed several key factors influencing their engagement in mathematics, including the usefulness of mathematics in daily life, intrinsic motivation, teacher influence, growth mindset, classroom dynamics, and practical applications. These findings suggest that fostering a supportive and non-judgmental classroom environment, emphasizing the practical relevance of math, and encouraging a growth mindset can enhance student engagement in mathematics. Teachers play a crucial role in shaping students' attitudes towards math by creating engaging and supportive learning experiences that challenge students while making them feel capable and motivated to succeed.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, several conclusions were drawn regarding the attitudes and behaviors of junior high school students toward mathematics. Firstly, Grade 9 students tend to believe that mathematics is a subject suited only for those with a natural inclination towards it. In contrast, Grade 8 students hold the belief that they can improve their mathematical abilities with effort. Secondly, the level of behavioral engagement, specifically in terms of participation and compliance, was observed to be only moderately present among junior high school students. Thirdly, there is a connection between the students' fixed mindset and their behavioral engagement in mathematics, particularly in areas such as attention, participation, and compliance, though this mindset did not correlate with their attendance in class. Lastly, Grade 7 students showed a positive correlation with all four indicators of behavioral engagement, suggesting that they find mathematics easier and are more open to improving their performance. In contrast, students in Grades 8, 9, and 10 generally perceive mathematics as a difficult subject.

Relative to the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were formulated:

The Department of Education should conduct training for the teachers that will help motivate the students and make them more interactive in the class. Further, the Department of Education should equip teachers with teaching strategies that could enhance behavioral engagement in mathematics.

The teachers should pursue graduate studies to improve their learning in the content of the subject matter they are teaching. The teachers should consider to integrate behavioral engagement activities in the classroom to help students understand the lesson. Teachers should have continual advancement in their teaching strategies to enable them to cope with the diversity of learners in the 21st –century.

The school should adopt a math mindset pre-assessment for the students during the beginning of the school year to determine the belief of the students towards the mathematics subject and to analyze what proper strategy is appropriate to apply in the teaching-learning process.

For future researchers who wish to enhance and/or use this study. The researchers suggest to develop an intervention that could help improve the student's mathematical mindset and may use another dependent variable to find new outcomes. Moreover, they encourage future researchers to further study this in the field of elementary level.

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